

A new 3-Dimensional model to describe the complete human corneal oxygenation during contact lens wear.

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Abstract

Purpose

This paper aims to provide a comprehensive 3-Dimensional (3-D) study quantifying oxygen tension, oxygen flux, and corneal oxygen consumption in different regions of the cornea (epithelium, stroma, and endothelium) when exposed to various contact lens materials. The study calculates the oxygen distribution profile within the cornea as a function of the oxygen tension at the cornea-tear interface, influenced by the oxygen transmissibility of the lens and the oxygen permeability values of the epithelium, stroma, and endothelium previously reported in literature.

Methods

Using an axisymmetric finite element analysis model, we conducted a new 3-D study on various contact lens materials and performed a parametric analysis of the effects of optical power. The permeability and transmissibility values of the lenses were measured in our laboratory. The oxygen permeability, diffusivity, solubility, thicknesses, and oxygen consumption rate considered for the epithelium, stroma, and endothelium were the same values used in a previously published work.

Results

The 3-D model presented in this study provides valuable insights into the flux and concentration profiles of oxygen across the epithelium, stroma, and endothelium. The key findings highlight the influence of contact lens thickness, which is related to its optical power, on the oxygen concentration within the cornea. Both parameters significantly

impact corneal flux and oxygen tension distribution. The reduction in corneal oxygen consumption occurs primarily in the epithelium, where the oxygen tension decreases in both under open-eye conditions and closed-eye conditions, depending on the type of contact lens worn and its power.

Keywords: 3-D model, optical power, corneal oxygen distribution, oxygen flux, oxygen tension, soft contact lens, Monod kinetics model.

1. Introduction

Understanding the oxygen demand of the cornea when using contact lenses has received in the last years significant attention, and numerous models have been developed [1-25]. Some of them assume a 1D geometry for oxygen transport through the cornea-tear-lens system, based on earlier works by Fatt and co-workers [4-6]. These models typically assume constant thickness and a constant oxygen consumption rate for the multilayer system, treating the diffusion equation only under steady-state conditions and neglecting time dependency [2-7]. However, such assumptions lead to negative partial pressure values within the cornea, which are physically unrealistic. To address this issue, recent mathematical models have focused on determining the oxygen tension at the cornea-tear interface, where the oxygen consumption rate is considered a function of pressure using the non-linear Monod kinetics model [8-24]. These models rely on knowledge of the partial pressure of oxygen at the cornea-tear interface, determined by Bonanno et al. using the technique of phosphorescence quenching of a dye coated the tear of a lens [9,18,19,21]. However, the majority of these models are limited to one-dimensional (1D) representations to try to explain the distribution of oxygen flux and consumption across different regions of the cornea, namely the epithelium, stroma, and endothelium [6-19].

In recent years, researchers have attempted to develop more realistic models by expanding to two-dimensional (2D) and three-dimensional (3D) representations [20-25]. For example, Alvord et al. [20] incorporated a realistic geometry of the cornea and lens system using a 2D axisymmetric finite element analysis (FEA) model to study corneal oxygen distribution with a 3.00D power contact lens. Their findings demonstrated the significance of lateral thickness, showing that 1D models underestimate oxygen demand across the entire cornea due to increased thickness in the periphery. Thus, considering lateral thickness variations becomes crucial when studying oxygen transport through the complete cornea, particularly with thick lenses such as scleral contact lenses.

More recently, Takatori et al. [23] and Kim et al. [21] introduced "quasi-2D" models that incorporated metabolic reactions involving carbon dioxide, glucose, lactate, and other substances within the corneal tissue. These models divided the cornea-tear-lens system into a series of truncated, concentric spherical sectors, effectively converting the three-dimensional diffusion into an axisymmetric system that approximates a 1D study. However, this approach disregards oxygen flow in the radial direction, limiting the incorporation of potential oxygen flows from the peripheral cornea as demonstrated by Alvord et al. [20], Kim et al. [21] and Takatori and Radke [23].

The advantage of Takatori's and Kim's models [19,21,23] over Alvord's model [20] lies in their incorporation of diffusion and metabolic reactions, such as carbon dioxide, glucose, lactate, bicarbonate, and hydrogen ions, within the cornea. However, Compañ et al. [24, 25] have developed a model that improves upon the work of Takatori [21] and Kim [23]. In this model, Compañ et al. provide a comprehensive 3D treatment with axial symmetry which facilitates the incorporation of the flux of multiple species. Moreover, it allows for the study of a wide range of lenses by constructing the six-layered system (endothelium-stroma-epithelium/tear/lens/tear) in real-time using a few parameters. Our model accounts for the maximum consumption rate, which occurs in the epithelium and is dependent on the oxygen tension at the cornea-tear-lens interface [24-26]. However, our previous models have limitations in that they assume the cornea is subjected to a specific contact lens with a given transmissibility and optical power (typically -3 diopters). This restricts their applicability to other geometries determined by the optical power of different contact lens materials.

The objective of this study is an improvement of the works previously carried out by our group where a 3D treatment with axial symmetry was implemented considering that the maximum consumption rate is focused on the epithelium, being a function of the corneal oxygen tension at the cornea/tear/lens interface [25]. Now, in this work, we provide a rigorous and more comprehensive treatment of diffusion in the cornea-tear-lens system, where the lens can have different transmissibility and optical power. For this purpose, we carried out the solution of 3D diffusion equations (with axial symmetry) and incorporated the possibility of oxygen in flux from the atmosphere through the peripheral corneal region and from aqueous humor. Our model considers contact lenses made of materials with any optical power, positive or negative, allowing for the modeling of arbitrary lenses under open-eye and closed-eye conditions using just a few input values. The numerical

solution of the transport equations generates a wide range of output values, including oxygen pressure profiles, oxygen flows, oxygen consumption, and integrated values across different parts of the cornea (epithelium, stroma, and endothelium).

Furthermore, our new model also calculates oxygen tension profiles from the central-to-peripheral cornea and can quantify metabolite transport to determine corneal edema. This enables the assessment of the effects of metabolite support from the vascularized limbus and the higher metabolic demand of the mid-peripheral and peripheral cornea during soft contact lens wear on corneal edema. In contrast, Alvord's model [20] cannot account for the effect of metabolite support from the limbus, and Takatori and Radke's model cannot assess radial metabolite flow, which may be significant depending on the geometry and parameters [23]. By incorporating metabolic support from the limbus and considering various transport mechanisms, our model offers a new tool to predict the oxygenation safety of contact lenses throughout the entire cornea.

Finally, this model, in addition to calculating the oxygen flux, oxygen consumption, and pressure profiles in each part of the cornea, can be easily modified to calculate steady-state and transitory profiles of other kinds of species as glucose or ions, such as lactate, bicarbonate, hydrogen, sodium, chloride, between others. All this, we think could help to understand the connection between metabolic reactions and oxygen transport which will be studied in future work.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Lens parameters

For this study, we have selected three contact lenses (CLs), one hydrogel (Hy), whose USAN name is Galyfilcon, and two Siloxane-Hydrogel (Si-Hy) whose names available in the European market are Balafilcon A and Lotrafilcon A. The characteristics of the lens, thickness, oxygen permeability, and transmissibility are given in Table 1. Technical details of CLs, reported by the manufacturer are also given with asterisks in Table 1. The oxygen tension at the interface cornea/tear/lens for the analyzed lenses has been previously obtained by Bonanno et al. [9,17] using the phosphorescence decay methodology.

Table 1. Physical parameters of the lens material (USAN name) used in this study. The values of oxygen solubility and diffusion coefficient of the lenses listed are in agreement with the paper of L.F. del Castillo et al. [1].

Lens Material (USAN name)	Manufac- turer	WC (%)	t (μm)	P (Barrer)	T (Barrer/cm)
Galyfilcon	J & J	47%	71*	59.4 (60*)	83.7 (85*)
Balafilcon A	Bausch & Lomb	36%	100*	107.0 (112*)	119.0 (124*)
Lotrafilcon A	Night&day	24%	80*	141.8 (140*)	177.3 (175*)

1 Barrer = 10^{-11} (cm²/s) (cm³(O₂)·cm⁻³ mmHg⁻¹).

(*) thickness measured by the manufacturer.

The values of the apparent transmissibility and permeability have been previously obtained in our laboratory following the polarographic method [27-30].

Physiological Parameters considered in the model

Table 2 shows the values and units we use in the new 3D model including separate corneal layer thickness, oxygen tensions at both anterior and posterior corneal surfaces of the total system: endothelium/stroma/epithelium/tear/lens/tear, below open and close eye conditions, and values of the maximum oxygen consumptions [15]. We also have considered a central cornea thickness of 532 μm, distributed in 50 μm for epithelium, 480 μm for stroma, and 2 μm for endothelium. The thickness peripheral will be dependent on the specific optical power of the lens. Finally, the values of the permeabilities of each part of the cornea, their diffusivities and solubilities have been consistent in the literature over the years, others have varied [15, 16, 19, 24-26, 31-33]. The value of the tears permeability was considered as 93 Barrer or Fatt units, considering that the oxygen diffusion coefficient (*D*) and solubility (*k*) of water at 25 °C are 30×10^{-6} cm²/s and 3.1×10^{-5} cm³(O₂)·cm⁻³·mmHg⁻¹, respectively [34]. Notice that cm³(O₂) refers to the equivalent oxygen quantity measured at standard temperature and pressure conditions (sTP), here and in all this work. The maximum oxygen consumption in the epithelium considered for each lens in the study was obtained from reference [25].

Table 2. Parameters considered to calculate the oxygen tension, the flux, and the oxygen consumption profiles, at endothelium, epithelium, and stroma in axis and periphery for open and closed-eye conditions considering our new 3D model.

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Units
Partial pressure of oxygen at the posterior corneal surface	p_{ac}	24.1	mmHg
Partial pressure of oxygen at the surface lens (open eye)	p_{air}	155	mmHg
Partial pressure of oxygen at the surface lens (closed eye)	p_{air}	61.5	mmHg
Maximum endothelium oxygen consumption	$Q_{max,end}$	47.78×10^{-5}	$cm^3(O_2) \cdot cm^{-3} \cdot s^{-1}$
Maximum stroma oxygen consumption	$Q_{max,es}$	5.75×10^{-5}	$cm^3(O_2) \cdot cm^{-3} \cdot s^{-1}$
Stroma oxygen permeability	$(DK)_{stroma}$	29.5	Barrer
Endothelium oxygen permeability	$(DK)_{end}$	5.3	Barrer
Epithelium oxygen permeability	$(DK)_{stroma}$	18.8	Barrer
Tear (water) oxygen permeability.	$(DK)_{tear}$	93	Barrer
Stroma oxygen diffusion coefficient	D_{stroma}	2.81×10^{-5}	cm^2/s
Endothelium oxygen diffusion coefficient	D_{end}	0.496×10^{-5}	cm^2/s
Epithelium oxygen diffusion coefficient	D_{stroma}	1.767×10^{-5}	cm^2/s
Central cornea thickness	CCT	532	μm
Epithelium thickness	t_{ep}	50	μm
Stroma thickness	t_{st}	480	μm
Endothelium thickness	t_{en}	2	μm
K_m (metabolic model parameter)	K_m	2.2	mmHg
Pre-Lens tear thickness (PrLTF)	$t_{lac,in}$	15	μm
Post-Lens tear thickness (PoLTF)	$t_{lac,ex}$	5	μm

1 Barrer = $10^{-11} (cm^2/s) (cm^3(O_2) \cdot cm^{-3} mmHg^{-1})$.

Theoretical model

Regarding the advantage of this work compared to Kim et al. [21], we find it necessary to highlight that we consider Kim's model to be flawed. Their model presents a 2-D diffusion in a section of the eye using Cartesian coordinates. However, in the diffusion equation, the term $\nabla \cdot (D_i \nabla c_i)$ represents a divergence that incorporates additional radial dependence, unlike the Cartesian case. In other words, when interpreting the two directions as cylindrical coordinates, this difference becomes crucial as it accounts for the increase in the area of the elements in the radial direction. Unfortunately, Kim et al. failed to incorporate this variation a priori in their "rectangular" coordinates, as can be seen in Appendix A of their work [21].

In our previous studies, we utilized FiPy [35], a Python-based finite volume approach, to numerically solve the partial differential equation (PDE). However, in this work, we employed COMSOL Multiphysics v6.2 for the numerical model implementation. COMSOL offers predefined physics interfaces for diffusion and reaction, along with tailored solvers that enable more accurate and less error-prone solutions. This enhanced integration allows us to introduce multiple species into the model.

To determine the lens shape corresponding to a specific optical power, we used the lens maker's equation, which relates the focal length of a lens to its material and geometry [36]. The equation is as follows:

$$P = \frac{1}{f} = (n - 1) \cdot \left(\frac{1}{R_2} - \frac{1}{R_1} + \frac{n-1}{n \cdot R_1 \cdot R_2} \cdot t_c \right) \quad (1)$$

Where P is the power in diopters, f is the focal length, n is the refractive index of the lens material, t_c is the central thickness of the lens, and R_1 and R_2 are the external and internal radii of the lens, respectively.

In this work, we obtained the refractive index of the lens material corresponding to -3 diopters and used it to generate the lens shape for other diopters. For negative diopters, the central thickness was maintained as the minimum thickness, while for positive diopters, the minimum thickness was set at the periphery. The geometry information was generated in Matlab®, and correlations as a function of the optical power were established to implement the position of the origin and periphery limits in the COMSOL geometry, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Lens shapes deduced from the optical power (diopters)

Figure 1 shows the thickness variation of lenses of both positive and negative powers. A close inspection of these figures shows that negative power lenses have a greater increase in thickness in the peripheral zone than positive power lenses. In the latter, the increase in thickness is observed in the axial zone, increasing the thickness as the optical power of the lens increases. Therefore, it is interesting to carry out a 3D study of the flow and consumption of oxygen in the lens, since the oxygen transmissibility of the lens is variable depending on the thickness of the lens, which in turn is a function of its optical power. On the other hand, we will be able to appreciate the differences in flow and consumption with respect to the studies carried out considering a one-dimensional analysis (1D).

In the COMSOL implementation, the dependent variable used was the oxygen concentration in each of the following domains: external tear, lens, internal tear, epithelium, stroma, and endothelium.

Assuming steady-state condition without convection, the conservation equation for a component i , molecular oxygen on our case, reduces to:

$$\nabla \cdot J_i = -Q_i \quad (2)$$

being Q_i the oxygen consumption and J_i the oxygen flux given by Fick's law as

$$J_i = -D_i \nabla c_i \quad (3)$$

Where c_i is the oxygen concentration in any point of the cornea, which can be written, taking into account Henry's law as $c_i = (k \cdot p)_i$, where k and p are the oxygen solubility and the oxygen tension at the point i , respectively. Taking into account the equations (2) and (3), we obtain:

$$\nabla \cdot (D_i \nabla c_i) = Q_i \quad (4)$$

To solve for the oxygen transport in the system (composed of endothelium, stroma, epithelium, tears layers, and lens), the oxygen consumption is given as a function of the oxygen partial pressure, being zero in the contact lens and tear film regions. Taking into account that aerobic metabolism in each layer in the corneal system is quantified by the Monod kinetics model [12], also named as Michaelis Menten Model [20,37,38] where the relation between oxygen consumption and oxygen tension is given by:

$$Q_{c,n}(p_{c,n}) = \frac{Q_{c,max,n} \cdot p(\vec{r})}{K_m + p(\vec{r})} \quad (5)$$

Where $Q_{c,max,n}$ is the maximum corneal oxygen consumption at domain n ($n =$ epithelium, stroma, or endothelium) when the reaction reaches the aforementioned steady-state conditions, and $p_{c,n}$ is the partial pressure of oxygen at n . In Eqs. (3) and (4), the solubility (k) and the diffusion coefficient (D) are considered a function of the position but take constant values within each of the different layers of the system (pre-lens tear, CL, post-lens tear, epithelium, stroma, and endothelium). The value of the Monod kinetics constant was $K_m = 2.2$ mmHg previously used by Chhabra et al. [11]. This value is based on the oxygen consumption from transient post-contact lens tear-film oxygen tension using the kinetics model and assuming that the cornea saturates at 90% oxygen consumption when the oxygen tension is 20 mmHg. Using the above approach, we can obtain the complete oxygen tension profile, the oxygen flux profile, and the oxygen consumption rate, provided that the continuity of the oxygen tension is satisfied in each one of the multiple interfaces considered in our cornea system. Dirichlet boundary conditions for oxygen tension were applied at the external interfaces as shown in Table 2. The equations were solved in 3D domains assuming axial symmetry. The partition conditions between domains were established according to the quotient between the oxygen solubility between both phases, and the Neumann boundary conditions (flux continuity) were satisfied in each interface.

Results

Figure 2 shows the oxygen tension profiles in open and closed eye conditions for the reference lens materials (Galyfilcon A, Balafilcon A, and Lotrafilcon A) for lenses of optical power of -3 diopters and $+3$ diopters. In the figures, we are including the oxygen tension through the radial axis and peripheral zone. Similar plots were obtained for the optical powers of -6 and $+6$ (see Supplementary Information, Figure S1).

The oxygen tension profile obtained was continuous. The main fall is produced in the lens, especially at the periphery, because of the minor transmissibility of the lens as consequence of the higher thickness in the periphery that in the center in case of lens materials with negative optical power.

Figure 2. Oxygen tension profiles in the axis and periphery of the eye for the three reference materials and optical powers -3 and $+3$ diopter in open-eye and closed-eye conditions.

A close inspection of the graphs in Figure 2 indicates a higher drop in oxygen tension at the periphery than in the axis zone for all lens materials, and optical powers regardless of the open-eye or closed-eye condition.

If we focus on a lens made of Galyfilcon A material with a negative optical power of -3 (Figure 2a) a narrow zone with very low oxygen tension close to ($200\ \mu\text{m}$ from the endothelium) is observed in the axis of the eye and under open-eye conditions. This zone for a lens with a positive optical power of $+3$ (Figure 2b) extends up to $400\ \mu\text{m}$. In both optical powers the zone of low oxygen concentrations extends up to $500\ \mu\text{m}$ from the endothelium in the closed-eye condition because of the low oxygen tension imposed in this condition. Comparing the results from the peripheral zone of the eyeball with those from the axis of the eye shows a shift of the curves, a consequence of the greater thickness of the cornea in the periphery, but also a greater amplitude in all cases of the low oxygen tension zone.

If the results obtained for Galyfilcon A are compared with those obtained for Balafilcon A (Figures 2c and 2d) and Lotrafilcon A (Figures 2e and 2f) under the same conditions, permit us to observe somewhat higher levels of oxygen tension as a consequence of the greater transmissibility to the oxygen from these lenses. These differences are somewhat more evident in the axis of the eye for the case of positive optical power and in the periphery for the case of negative optical power because of the greater thickness in each area in these situations. Notice that for a lens made of Balafilcon A material with a negative optical power of -3 (Figure 2c) a narrow zone with very low oxygen tension close to ($200\ \mu\text{m}$ from the endothelium) is observed in the axis of the eye and under open-eye conditions. This zone for a lens with a positive optical power of $+3$ (Figure 2d) extends up to $490\ \mu\text{m}$, while in the case of Lotrafilcon A extends until $480\ \mu\text{m}$ (Figure 2f). In both optical powers, the zone of low oxygen concentrations extends up to $500\ \mu\text{m}$ from the endothelium in the closed-eye condition as a consequence of the low oxygen tension imposed in this condition.

Positive-power lenses are more problematic than negative-power lenses because they are thicker throughout their profile, as shown in Figures 2b, 2d, and 2f. This thickness leads to lower O_2 tension values in most of the stroma region, especially in the closed-eye condition. Also, it is remarkable that positive-power lenses have a variation of width that compensates for the change in width in the cornea. That's the reason for the different axial distances covered between Figures 2a and 2b.

Figure 2a compares nicely with Figure 2 of reference [25], where the same lens (Galyfilcon A lens of -3 diopters) was studied using a different numerical procedure based on FiPy [35]. Here in this new 3D model, we can benefit from the additional effect of the lens geometry using lenses of additional power.

On the other hand, if we compare the decrease in oxygen tension between the tear/epithelium and epithelium/stroma interfaces we can observe a decrease from 100 to 40 mmHg for Galyfilcon A, from 60 to 10 mmHg in the axis and periphery respectively under OE conditions and optical power of -3 diopters. For Balafilcon A lenses, these values vary between 108 to 45 mmHg in the axis and between 80 to 20 mmHg for the periphery under the same conditions. While for Lotrafilcon A lenses our model indicates that these values vary from 120 to 45 mmHg in the axis and from 100 to 30 mmHg in the periphery under OE conditions. Considering the same materials but an optical power of $+3$ diopters, these values change, being these variations between 60 to 10 mmHg in the axis and 85 to 20 in the periphery for Galyfilcon A lens, from 72 to 20 mmHg in the axis and 100 to 30 mmHg at the periphery, in the case of Balafilcon A, while this values varying between 100 to 30 mmHg in the axis and between 120 to 35 mmHg in the periphery for Lotrafilcon A lenses.

Figure 3 depicts the results of our 3D model calculations for the magnitude of oxygen flux, both under open-eye and closed-eye conditions, using the three different lenses with -3 diopters and $+3$ diopters. The flux magnitude is plotted near the axis and periphery of the eye, represented by the solid and dashed lines, respectively. A similar representation is shown in Supplementary Information Figure SI2 for -6 and $+6$ diopters. As expected, the effect of geometry is evident. For the -3 -diopter lens (Fig. 3a, 3c, 3e), the flux is lower near the periphery where the lens is thicker. Conversely, for the $+3$ diopter lenses (Fig. 3b, 3d, 3f), the flux is higher near the periphery due to the thinner lens. Some discontinuities are observed as a result of the finite discretization used. In the previous 3D model [25] we obtained an oxygen flux under open-eye conditions in the interface epithelium/tear of $12.8 \mu\text{L}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$, in the stroma/epithelium $3.34 \mu\text{L}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ and the endothelium/stroma $2.43 \mu\text{L}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$. Under closed-eye conditions, those values were 7.11, 0.55, and $2.36 \mu\text{L}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ respectively for the same lens. In the Balafilcon A lens, the values were 14.45, 3.05 and, $2.43 \mu\text{L}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ under open-eye conditions for epithelium/tear, stroma/epithelium, and endothelium/stroma respectively, and 8.01, 0.42, and 2.36 under closed-eye conditions for the same lens and interfaces as before. Finally, in the case of a Lotrafilcon A lens, we obtained values of 14.94, 4.08, and 2.43

$\mu\text{L}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ under open eye, and 9.34, 0.84, and 2.36 $\mu\text{L}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ under closed-eye conditions, respectively in the epithelium/tear, stroma/epithelium, and endothelium/stroma interfaces. All these values compare very well with those reported in this work (see Table 3).

The decrease in flux is influenced by both the geometry particularly in the lens depending on the optical power and oxygen consumption in the corneal region.

In Table 3 we can see for the three lens materials studied the estimated values of the oxygen flux in ($\mu\text{L}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$) exchanged between the different parts of the cornea (tear/epithelium, epithelium/stroma, and stroma/endothelium) analyzed from the 3D model near the axis A ($0^\circ - 13.6^\circ$), middle ring M ($13.6^\circ - 27.3^\circ$), and peripheral ring P ($27.3^\circ - 41^\circ$) areas.

Table 3. Oxygen flux ($\mu\text{L}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$) exchanged between corneal layers wearing lenses of different materials and optical power (O.P.), under open-eye and closed-eye conditions and for different areas of the cornea.[A: axis area ($0-13.6^\circ$), M: middle ring ($13.6^\circ-27.3^\circ$), and P: peripheral ring ($27.3^\circ-41^\circ$); te>ep: from external tear to epithelium, ep>st: from epithelium to stroma, en>st: from endothelium to stroma, in>en: received internally by endothelium]

Material	O.P.	Exchange	Open-eye			Closed-eye		
			A	M	P	A	M	P
Galyfilcon	-3	te>ep	12.46	12.21	11.54	7.32	6.73	5.76
		ep>st	3.66	3.03	1.80	0.46	0.25	0.08
		en>st	2.67	2.66	2.64	2.68	2.66	2.64
		in>en	2.99	3.00	3.01	3.00	3.00	3.01
	+3	te>ep	9.49	10.22	11.87	4.37	4.84	6.06
		ep>st	1.37	1.53	2.01	0.07	0.07	0.09
		en>st	2.68	2.66	2.64	2.68	2.66	2.64
		in>en	3.00	3.00	3.01	3.00	3.00	3.01
Balafilcon A	-3	te>ep	16.07	15.97	15.46	9.24	8.73	7.85
		ep>st	3.08	2.45	1.29	0.19	0.10	0.03
		en>st	2.68	2.66	2.64	2.68	2.66	2.64
		in>en	3.00	3.00	3.01	3.00	3.00	3.01
	+3	te>ep	13.64	14.45	16.20	6.62	7.17	8.51
		ep>st	1.41	1.46	1.65	0.05	0.04	0.04
		en>st	2.68	2.66	2.64	2.68	2.66	2.64
		in>en	3.00	3.00	3.01	3.00	3.00	3.01
Lotrafilcon A	-3	te>ep	14.18	14.27	14.31	9.08	8.77	8.16
		ep>st	4.19	3.77	2.90	0.69	0.45	0.18
		en>st	2.67	2.66	2.64	2.68	2.66	2.64

	in>en	2.99	3.00	3.01	3.00	3.00	3.01
+3	te>ep	12.85	13.41	14.56	7.08	7.51	8.49
	ep>st	3.02	3.03	3.10	0.23	0.22	0.21
	en>st	2.68	2.66	2.64	2.68	2.66	2.64
	in>en	3.00	3.00	3.01	3.00	3.00	3.01

Figure 3. Oxygen flux profiles in the axis and periphery of the eye for the three reference materials and optical powers -3 and $+3$ diopter in open-eye and closed-eye conditions.

Values of oxygen flux in Figure 3a reproduce very closely the results obtained in Figure 2 reference [25], except for a small difference probably resulting from the more precisely defined geometry meshing of the present work. Additionally, in Figure 3b we find the strong influence of geometry through the study of a positive power Galyfilcon lens (+3 diopter). This gives a ~24% reduction in the oxygen flux near de eye axis under open eye conditions when going from a Galyfilcon -3-diopter lens ($12.46 \mu\text{L}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$) to a +3-diopter lens ($9.49 \mu\text{L}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$). The influence is lower near the periphery of the system, which shows the complex interplay between the geometry of the lens and the cornea in determining the oxygen flow and distribution in the cornea-lens system.

The results obtained in this work validate our previous studies in similar systems [25], but also give a nice perspective of 1D models when the 3D model is applied to identical lens materials. A close inspection of the work carried out by Compañ et al. [24] where a Balafilcon A lens (and many others) was studied using a 1D diffusion model with an oxygen consumption rate given by the Monod kinetics model, permits us to conclude that the oxygen flux through the axis of the eye for the case of positive optical power was quite similar.

Figure 5 in [24] contains values of oxygen flux that compare well with our values. For example, for Balafilcon A lens we find an oxygen flux at the epithelium/tear of about $15 \mu\text{L}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ [24] under open eye, very close to the value in this work of about $16.07 \mu\text{L}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ near the axis (see Table 3). However, for the Galyfilcon A lens material the discrepancy is around of 7% for the values in the stroma region where the value was of $\sim 2.4 \mu\text{L}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$, compared to the value of $\sim 2.6 \mu\text{L}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ in this work under open-eye conditions. The differences are less apparent under closed-eye conditions, which makes it difficult to predict the failure of the 1D model a priori. All models have a nice coincidence near the endothelium where values of oxygen tension and consequently fluxes and consumption are strongly determined by the close inner boundary condition. A comparison of the values of the 1D model and the 3D model in this work seems to support the idea that a 1D model compares more favorably to the transport of oxygen near to the eye axis. A comparison between the oxygen flux values in axis between this model, which values are 12.46 , 3.66 and $2.67 \mu\text{L}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ at the interfaces ep/te, st/ep and en/st, respectively for Galyfilcon A lens. Following the 1D model used in reference [16], the values obtained for the oxygen flux were 9.21 , 3.46 and $5.09 \mu\text{L}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ and 12.80 , 3.34 and $2.43 \mu\text{L}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ following 3D at the same interfaces for the same lens material and

same optical power (-3 diopters). Similar discrepancies were observed for the other materials Balafilcon A and Lotrafilcon A.

Finally, we have validated the results for oxygen flux in this work to our previous work and found a nice correspondence. For example, the values of a Galyfilcon lens of -3 diopters were $12.8 \mu\text{L}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ and $7.11 \mu\text{L}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ under open-eye and closed-eye conditions respectively (see [25]) and very close to the average values obtained in our work (see values given in Table 3), which values for the same lens are $12.07 \mu\text{L}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ and $6.6 \mu\text{L}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ under the same conditions. In case of Balafilcon A lens, these values are $14.45 \mu\text{L}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ and $8.6 \mu\text{L}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ under open-eye and closed-eye conditions respectively, while in this work the values are 15.83 and $8.31 \mu\text{L}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$, respectively. Finally, for the Lotrafilcon Lens materials the obtained values of average oxygen flux at the epithelium/tear interface were 14.25 and $8.37 \mu\text{L}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$, under open-eye and closed-eye conditions, respectively. These values are quite similar to the obtained in our previous 3D model [25], whose values were 14.94 and $9.34 \mu\text{L}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$, respectively.

A clear observation of the variation of oxygen flux with the power of the lens for the same material allows us to indicate that in negative power lenses, the oxygen flux through the cornea is mostly produced radially in both open and closed eyes. However, in the case of positive power lenses, this flux can be seen to be given by both contours, of the transmissibility of the lens. Bear in mind that in the case of positive lenses, they have a greater thickness in the direction of the axis (radial) and less in the peripheral direction, which allows for greater diffusion through the periphery than through the axis of the lens.

For the lens with negative optical power, flux in the axis (angle from axis near zero) is higher than that in the periphery because of the higher lens thickness in the periphery. In this case, for open-eye conditions, the oxygen transferred from the epithelium to the stroma is higher than that received by the stroma from the endothelium up to an angle with respect to the axis of about 32° . For closed-eye conditions, the oxygen flux received from the internal tear is substantially decreased and most of the oxygen is received from the endothelium.

For positive optical power, the situation is reversed because of the higher thickness in the center lens compared to that in the periphery. For open-eye conditions, the stroma can receive more oxygen from the tear and epithelium than from the endothelium at extreme periphery positions. For closed-eye conditions, the oxygen coming from the tear is also

substantially decreased and the oxygen received from the endothelium overwhelmingly predominates.

Figure 4 displays the magnitude of the oxygen flux crossing the interfaces between domains (from tear to epithelium, from epithelium to stroma, and from endothelium to stroma) in open-eye and closed-eye conditions using the three reference materials (Galyfilcon A, Balafilcon A, and Lotrafilcon A lenses with -3 diopter (left panels) and $+3$ diopter (right panels)). Supplementary Information Figure S3 displays the cases of -6 and $+6$ diopter. Despite differences in materials and geometries, common features emerge. The oxygen flux at the endothelium-stroma interface is nearly independent of the distance from the axis center, suggesting that the lens geometry has minimal influence on oxygen diffusion in the innermost layer of the cornea.

In contrast, the oxygen flux crossing the epithelium-stroma interface exhibits a variety of behaviors. The crossing between the lines corresponding to the almost constant endothelium-stroma and epithelium-stroma flux indicates a reversal of the dominant oxygen flux. Lenses with higher transmissibilities and/or lower thicknesses (as shown in Table 3) only cause a slight flux reversal, as seen in the case of Lotrafilcon A (Figure 8), except under closed-eye conditions. In the latter case, a consistently lower oxygen flux is observed crossing the epithelium-stroma interface compared to the endothelium-stroma interface.

Furthermore, we observe a significantly increased flux of oxygen, even under closed-eye conditions, crossing the tear-epithelium interface for all the materials and geometries studied. This highlights the substantial reduction in flux over the short distance between the tear-epithelium and epithelium-stroma interfaces due to higher consumption in the epithelium (not included in Table 3).

Figure 4. Oxygen flux exchanged between eye layers as a function of the angle taken from the eye axis for the three reference materials and optical powers -3 and $+3$ diopter in open-eye and closed-eye conditions.

In Figures 5 and 6, we plotted the oxygen consumption in each layer of the system for Galyfilcon A for -3 and $+3$ diopters respectively. Similar figures can be found for Balafilcon A and Lotrafilcon A lenses in Supplementary Information Figures S4 – S7. All figures include both open-eye (top) and closed-eye (bottom) conditions. We observe that in all cases, the higher consumption occurs near the endothelium and epithelium regions. However, under closed-eye conditions, Galyfilcon lenses exhibit reduced consumption. Recognizing that consumption is related to local oxygen concentration, areas of lower

consumption correspond to regions of hypoxia, indicating less ideal material performance under these conditions.

Another interesting observation is the compensating effect of positive power lenses on the uneven distribution of oxygen along the cornea. Due to their thinning near the edges of the system, these lenses compensate for the increased thickness of the cornea. As a result, there is a more homogeneous distribution of oxygen consumption as we move away from the axis of the system, as shown in Figures 5 and 6.

Furthermore, Figures 5, 6 and Supplementary Figures S1-S4 provide a clear indication that, although all materials exhibit similar behaviors under negative power lenses, there is a slight advantage observed in the case of Lotrafilcon A lenses. This advantage is likely due to their higher permeability, which leads to a higher oxygen consumption compared to Galyfilcon A lenses.

Figure 5. Corneal contour graphs of oxygen consumption wearing a Galyfilcon A lens of -3 diopters under open-eye (up) and closed-eye condition (down). The bar relates color to oxygen consumption expressed in $\text{cm}^3(\text{O}_2) \cdot \text{cm}^{-3} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$.

Figure 6. Corneal contour graphs of oxygen consumption wearing a Galyfilcon A lens of +3 diopters in open-eye (up) and closed-eye condition (down). The color bar relates color to oxygen consumption expressed in $\text{cm}^3(\text{O}_2) \cdot \text{cm}^{-3} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$.

The sum of the oxygen consumption rates for each point of the epithelium, stroma, and endothelium will give the total corneal oxygen consumption value. These results for open-eye or close-eye conditions are shown in Table 4. The averages of oxygen consumption in the selected zones (axis, middle ring, and periphery of the eye) show quantitatively important differences caused by the lens. The most significant difference would be between the axis and the periphery zones for the Galyfilcon A lens of +6 diopters under OE condition where a relative difference of 54% was obtained.

Table 4. Average oxygen consumption ($10^{-6} \text{ cm}^3(\text{O}_2)\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$) for different lens materials, eye condition, and optical powers (O.P.) in different areas of epithelium and stroma: axis area (A, $0-13.6^\circ$); middle ring (M, $13.6^\circ-27.3^\circ$); and peripheral ring (P, $27.3^\circ-41^\circ$).

Material	Eye	O.P.	epithelium			stroma		
			A	M	P	A	M	P
Galyfilcon	open	-6	502.1	489.4	431.9	35.2	27.1	16.0
		-3	503.1	497.4	476.8	35.9	30.2	20.7
		+3	459.7	467.6	483.5	22.0	21.5	21.8
		+6	377.4	402.0	457.1	16.6	16.2	17.9
	closed	-6	377.5	309.1	213.1	16.6	14.3	12.1
		-3	385.4	343.6	272.3	16.8	14.7	12.3
		+3	238.8	251.0	286.3	14.7	13.8	12.3
		+6	167.8	184.6	241.1	14.5	13.6	12.1
Balafilcon A	open	-6	504.5	498.6	475.5	37.1	30.8	20.5
		-3	505.0	501.9	492.6	37.6	32.8	24.6
		+3	492.9	494.7	498.6	30.0	28.7	27.0
		+6	463.9	473.3	490.4	22.6	22.5	23.8
	closed	-6	399.2	351.1	270.2	17.4	14.9	12.3
		-3	404.0	374.3	318.1	17.6	15.4	12.6
		+3	318.9	326.5	347.5	15.4	14.4	12.9
		+6	244.8	261.4	309.8	14.7	13.8	12.5
Lotrafilcon A	open	-6	507.6	504.3	493.5	40.2	34.7	25.1
		-3	507.9	506.0	500.9	40.5	36.1	28.4
		+3	500.5	501.2	502.7	34.1	32.2	29.4
		+6	487.6	491.3	498.5	27.9	27.3	27.0
	closed	-6	432.7	396.3	323.1	19.3	16.1	12.7
		-3	435.8	413.3	364.6	19.5	16.8	13.2
		+3	364.0	367.3	377.6	16.2	15.1	13.4
		+6	298.0	311.4	347.6	15.1	14.2	12.9

For the endothelium, the values obtained in the axis area, middle, and peripheral ring were practically the same (4.353×10^{-4} , 4.351×10^{-4} , and $4.348\times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^3(\text{O}_2)\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ respectively) for all optical powers, materials, and eye-conditions studied. For this reason, these values are not included in Table 4.

Discussion

It is well-established that a decrease in oxygen tension results in reduced oxygen flow and consumption, prompting a shift in corneal physiology towards anaerobic metabolism, thereby increasing lactate production and leading to corneal swelling³⁹. Our 3D modeling predicts that under open-eye (OE) conditions, the oxygen tension profiles and flux for specific anterior corneal surface P_{O_2} values exceed 60 mmHg across all lens materials studied, both centrally and peripherally. This suggests that these lenses, ranging from optical powers of +3 to -3 diopters, provide higher oxygen tension values to the human cornea compared to the closed-eye (CE) environment, where the palpebral conjunctiva typically provides a value around 60 mmHg^{5,8,15}.

Through a combination of modeling and experimentation, a critical oxygen tension (COT) ranging from 70 to 125 mmHg has been proposed as the threshold below which corneal physiology becomes compromised, leading to corneal edema and other associated metrics⁴⁰⁻⁴⁴. Our new 3D model yields average oxygen flux values into the corneal epithelium of approximately $7.5 \mu\text{L}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ for Galyfilcon A lenses, $9.1 \mu\text{L}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ for Balafilcon A lenses, and $8.9 \mu\text{L}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ for Lotrafilcon A lenses in cases of negative optical power. Conversely, for positive optical power, these values are predicted to be 6.1, 8.1, and $8.3 \mu\text{L}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ for Galyfilcon A, Balafilcon A, and Lotrafilcon A lenses, respectively, under OE conditions at sea level. Notably, these results align more closely with those of Takatory et al.¹⁹ than with previous findings by Jauregui and Fatt³².

It is noteworthy that all lenses studied predict average oxygen flux values (both centrally and peripherally) that gradually decrease towards a corneal tear interface P_{O_2} above 70 mmHg for negative optical powers (-3 diopters) and very close to this value for positive optical powers (+3 diopters). This value is comparable or slightly higher than that observed under the closed eyelid condition⁴⁵. With these average oxygen flux and oxygen tension values at the epithelium/tears interface, we postulate that the epithelial layer would be adequately supported to maintain optimal physiological conditions when such lenses are worn on the human cornea.

A comparison of the values in Table 4 with previous models highlights the limitations of 1D models [24] for accurately depicting the oxygen transport mechanisms in corneal lenses. One of the primary shortcomings of 1D models, such as the one described in [24],

lies in their inability to account for intricate details like optical power. These models are restricted to incorporating lens thickness as the sole geometric characteristic of the lens, which can significantly impair their ability to replicate the intricate oxygen transport dynamics within the corneal tissue. Nevertheless, despite this significant limitation, the results obtained from 1D models generally align well with those obtained from more sophisticated 3D models. The most notable discrepancy arises in the overestimation of oxygen consumption rates by 1D models. For instance, for a Balafilcon A lens of power -3 under OE conditions, the 1D model [24] predicts oxygen consumption rates of $5.85 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^3(\text{O}_2) \cdot \text{cm}^{-3} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ and $4.9 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^3(\text{O}_2) \cdot \text{cm}^{-3} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ in the epithelium and stroma, respectively. In contrast, our 3D model predicts significantly lower consumption rates of $5.04 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^3(\text{O}_2) \cdot \text{cm}^{-3} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ and $3.71 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^3(\text{O}_2) \cdot \text{cm}^{-3} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, respectively. Similar discrepancies are observed for CE conditions, with the 1D model predicting consumption rates of $4.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^3(\text{O}_2) \cdot \text{cm}^{-3} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ and $2.8 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^3(\text{O}_2) \cdot \text{cm}^{-3} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ in the epithelium and stroma, respectively, compared to our 3D model predictions of $4.04 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^3(\text{O}_2) \cdot \text{cm}^{-3} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ and $1.76 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^3(\text{O}_2) \cdot \text{cm}^{-3} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, respectively. It is noteworthy that the differences between our 3D model and other 3D models [25] are relatively minor. For example, in the case of the Balafilcon A lens material under OE conditions, the oxygen consumption rates observed were $5.83 \cdot 10^{-4}$ and $2.84 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^3(\text{O}_2) \cdot \text{cm}^{-3} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ in epithelium and stroma respectively, while under CE conditions, we obtained $4.55 \cdot 10^{-4}$ and $1.55 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^3(\text{O}_2) \cdot \text{cm}^{-3} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, respectively for the same lens and power as above. These findings underscore the overall accuracy of our 3D model in capturing the oxygen transport dynamics within corneal lenses, even under varying conditions.

The subtleties present in the use of lenses of different optical power, which can lead to changes in consumption of more than 100% (Table 4 in the epithelium of a Galyfilcon A lens of powers -6 and $+6$) can only be explored correctly with a model such as the one presented in this work, leaving them out of the options of simpler 1D models.

Finally, our results estimate an average of oxygen consumption rate at epithelium around 4.92×10^{-4} , 5.00×10^{-4} , and $5.05 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^3(\text{O}_2) \cdot \text{cm}^{-3} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, for Galyfilcon A, Balafilcon A and Lotrafilcon A, respectively, working below open-eye conditions, and 3.34×10^{-4} , 3.66×10^{-4} , and $4.05 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^3(\text{O}_2) \cdot \text{cm}^{-3} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, for Galyfilcon A, Balafilcon A and Lotrafilcon A, respectively, working below closed-eye conditions. These results are higher than the values used by Alvord et al. as parameters used in his 1D model based on 2005 BEL model, which value utilized was $2.59 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^3(\text{O}_2) \cdot \text{cm}^{-3} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$.

Lastly, it is important to emphasize that all the findings presented in this study rely on the application of the nonlinear Monod Kinetics model, which posits that corneal oxygen consumption is a result of aerobic metabolism influenced by oxygen tension, as described by equation (5) proposed by Chhabra et al.^{11,12} Other researchers have proposed a similar equation but with a different value for the parameter K_m , substituting 0.5 for the value of 2.2 used by Chhabra. This discrepancy in K_m values stems from considerations of mitochondrial activity in cell respiration under hypoxic conditions⁴⁶. Under this premise, the minimum observed oxygen flux into the stroma (Figure 3) and oxygen tension (Figure 2) would shift towards the aqueous humor.

Conclusions

In conclusion, this study aims to enhance prior investigations conducted by our group, focusing on a 3D treatment with axial symmetry in the context of corneal oxygen dynamics. Our previous works concentrated on the epithelium, acknowledging its maximal oxygen consumption rate as a function of corneal oxygen tension at the cornea/tear/lens interface. In this endeavor, we present a more rigorous and comprehensive treatment of diffusion in the cornea-tear-lens system, accommodating lenses with different permeability and optical power.

Our approach involves solving 3D diffusion equations (with axial symmetry) and integrating the possibility of oxygen influx from the atmosphere through the peripheral corneal region and from the aqueous humor. The model accommodates contact lenses with varying optical powers, facilitating the modeling of arbitrary lenses under open-eye and closed-eye conditions using minimal input values. Numerical solutions of the transport equations yield diverse output parameters, including oxygen pressure profiles, flows, consumption rates, and integrated values across different corneal layers (epithelium, stroma, and endothelium).

Importantly, our novel model calculates oxygen tension profiles from the central-to-peripheral cornea, allowing for the quantification of metabolite transport and assessment of corneal edema. This permits the evaluation of the impact of metabolite support from the vascularized limbus and the heightened metabolic demand of the mid-peripheral and peripheral cornea during soft contact lens wear on corneal edema. Notably, existing models by Alvord and Takatori-Radke lack these capabilities.

By incorporating limbal metabolic support and considering various transport mechanisms, our model provides a valuable tool for predicting the oxygenation safety of contact lenses across the entire cornea. Furthermore, the model can be easily adapted to calculate steady-state and transient profiles of other species such as glucose, lactate, bicarbonate, hydrogen, sodium, and chloride, among others. We anticipate that these enhancements will contribute to a deeper understanding of the interplay between metabolic reactions and oxygen transport, paving the way for future studies in this domain.

The decrease in oxygen consumption leads to a physiological shift towards anaerobic metabolism over aerobic metabolism, resulting in elevated lactate production and consequent corneal swelling. Through a combination of computational models and experimental investigations, we postulate the existence of a "critical oxygen tension" specific to the anterior cornea, below which corneal physiology becomes compromised, leading to edema where a range compress between 70 and 125 mmHg of oxygen tension at the interface cornea/lens, is necessary to avoid hypoxic complications into the cornea such as corneal swelling, loss of transparency, corneal edema, corneal stroma acidosis, epithelial punctate staining, limbal hyperemia and endothelial polymegathism.

Figure 2 illustrates that aerobic metabolism is sustained down to the cornea-tear interface (anterior corneal surface) at partial pressure of oxygen (P_{O_2}) values approximately ranging from 60 to 100 mmHg. This phenomenon holds true across all contact lens types studied in this work under open-eye conditions. Conversely, under closed-eye conditions, aerobic metabolism is not adequately maintained, predisposing the cornea to anaerobic metabolism and subsequent edema upon prolonged exposure to such conditions.

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